

LOCAL GOVERNMENT COMMISSION AWKA AND LABOUR CONFLICT: THE PLIABILITY OF LABOUR AND MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: *Labour conflict is a recurrent decimal in Nigeria public service especially the Local Government System. It is on this backdrop that the study examined labour conflict and management strategies in Anambra State Local Government Service Commission Awka. Descriptive survey research design was found most appropriate for the study. Data were elicited from respondents using questionnaire, in-depth interview, focus group discussion guide. Pearson moment correlation was the analytical tool used in data analysis and test of hypotheses. The study revealed that lack of financial autonomy is responsible for frequent labour conflict in Anambra State Local Government Service Commission. Leadership style also has correlation with labour conflict in the System. In the light of the foregoing, we recommend that the Anambra State Local Government Service Commission should push for the complete fiscal autonomy of the local Government system in Nigeria. Also, the Service Commission should adopt workers friendly leadership style that will be democratic.*

1. Introduction

Government interest in regulating job relations in Nigeria dates back to colonial period with the passing of the Trade Union Ordinance of 1938 by the colonialists and the Trade Dispute (Inquiry and Arbitration) Decree of 1941 (Akpala, 1984).

According to Chukwu, (2001) the state is the highest regulator of employment concerning trade unions and their recognition with employers and the relationship between the employer and the unions in the collective bargaining.

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As Chukwuemeka and Aniche (2016) stated, industrial relation is the respective roles of management, labour and government in the process, which relates workers to employers, workers to workers, and workers to work.

Chukwuemeka and Aniche (2016) have brought out the concept more clearly in listing the participants or action of industrial relations as:

- (a) A hierarchy of managers and their representatives or representative organizations
- (b) A hierarchy of workers (non-managers and their spokesmen workers organization representatives.
- (c) Specialized governmental agencies that may include specialized private agencies created by the first two factors.

There is a tripartite employment relationship among the state, the union and the employer in making and enforcing job rules. The relationship presupposes a congenial and equal participation in issues affecting any of the parties.

Therefore, good industrial relation management is vital to the productivity of workers in organization, considering that management has been defined as the process of combining and utilizing or allocating an organizations inputs (man, materials and money) for planning, organizing, directing and controlling to the purpose of providing goods and services or whatever the objectives are (Akpala, 1993).

Poor management is bound to occur in an organization with inappropriate or wrong industrial relations management within the

organizations framework. Therefore, employers should involve in industrial relations in determining vital issues that affect workers, such as their working conditions, settlement of disputes as they arise, as there are likely to make workers to feel accepted, thereby enhancing productivity in the organization. Again, industrial relation, is a machinery used by both the employers of labour and employees to reach a compromise for job value, wages, salaries and increase in productivity of employees. To enhance productivity of workers as regards industrial relations management, industrial relations officials are elected by the employees to represent them, although at times, the employers of labour are also involved in appointing officials of such unions. In such cases, the interest of the employers are safeguarded, and the activities of the union are controlled by the employers of labour. Industrial relations management not only enhances productivity of the workers, but it also helps in settling disputes through collective bargaining, in the areas of job satisfaction job regulation and job rules.

The great strike of 1945 was a watershed in labour management relations in Nigeria (Ejiofor and Aniagoh, 1984). Several days have been lost to strikes, lockouts, sit-ins, picketing, suspension and dismissals since the colonial era to present day (Ukata, P. F., & Silas-Dikibo, I. D. (2020)

From the colonial days labour conflict and strike have become a regular occurrence, not only in

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the local government system, but in other sectors of the Nigerian Economy. For instance, strike actions moved from 30 cases in 1956/57 to 49 cases in 1957/58 and further to 53 in 1958/59 with corresponding increase in loss of resources (Imaga, 1990). Disputes between 1955/56 and 1958/59 led to the loss of a total of 974, 095 days to strike in Nigeria (Chukwuemeka and Aniche 2016). In 1982, a total of 8,221,761 days were lost to strikes involving 756, 394 workers, including the Nigerian Union of Local Government Employees – NULGE (Imaga, 1990). Between January and May, 1983, a total of 1,439,759 days were lost by the strikes of 259, 039 workers; Ninety-one trade disputes occurred of which 64% resulted in strikes (Otobo, 1988).

Chukwuemeka, Anazodo and Nzewi (2011) revealed that between 1993 to 1996, millions of days were lost to strikes by workers of the Local Government Councils across Nigeria over conditions of service. These revelations indicated an increase in the dimensions of labour management conflict is an inherent part of human interactions, particularly within organizational settings where diverse perspectives, interests, and values converge. An organization exists to provide goods and services that people desire. These goods and services are the products of the behaviours of workers who occupy different levels of the organizational structure. These workers also have various backgrounds, attitudes, traits, and points of view; and these diversities have the potentials to

cause friction, disagreements/arguments, differences or incompatibilities, and discrepancies that if not properly managed, may lead to conflict.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

One of the most fundamental problems currently destabilizing the survival of Nigerian Local Government System is the issue of labour conflict and management. Most of the Local Government workers are very often restless and confrontational in their approach to issues which affect them as a group, such as the government not fulfilling some of the employment contracts between it and the workers. As a result, they adopt anti-government posture which if care is not taken can tear the state apart.

The government of Nigeria always perceive the workers as lazy, uncooperative individuals, who always hold secret labour meetings and plan drastic actions against government, as well as any organization they consider a threat to the labour interest, while the workers in turn perceive the government as exploiting them. It is this perceptual basis arising from the government and the workers that sometimes serve as the “brewing pot” of the conflict. Thus, the Local Government Service Commission Awka has turned to a breeding ground for conflicts. The problem has been compounded by the financial autonomy issue which eventually led to a strike action in the year 2001. The strike involved all the arms of the Nigerian Union of Local Government Employees (NULGE),

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especially in the Southern part of the country. The nation lost a great deal in terms of financial and material resources.

Many practitioners have erroneously emphasized the role of management at the expense of labour and management. Also crucial is the attitude of government to labour. Government interventions in the field of industrial democracy are not usually explained properly to the half educated and unskilled labour. This has always resulted in spontaneous and unguided attack of almost all management decisions and policies as they relate to labour management relations, within the industrial environment. Government has always made policies concerning labour without labour's consultation. Wages and Salaries are fixed by fiat, the paradox thesis that despite the numerous judicial commission's and reform's recommendations and countless government white papers on Nigeria Local Government System, the problem of Labour- Management conflict has remained intractable and no meaningful progress has been made. In short, the problem is much more confounding than meet the eye, particularly when one realizes that the aims of creating the local government system are yet to be attained in most parts of the country, especially in Anambra State.

The central questions that will therefore form the basis of this inquiry are:

1. How can we explain the *raison d' et re* for management – labour conflict in Anambra

State local government Service Commission, in other words, is there any relationship between conditions of service of workers and the endless labour unrest?

2. What is the relationship between the nature of management leadership approach and the degree of labour conflict?

3. Is there any relationship between workers' participation in decision making in the local government administration and effective management of labour conflict?

1.3 Objectives of the Study

1. To find out the *raison d' et re* for management- labour conflict in Anambra State Local Government Service Commission.

2. To examine the relationship between the nature of management leadership approach and the degree of labour conflict.

3. To examine the relationship between meaningful workers participation in decision making in Anambra State Local Government Service Commission/.

1.4 Hypotheses

1. Labour conflict in Anambra State Local Government Service Commission is as a result of financial autonomy.

2. Leadership/management style is *raison d'et re* for labour conflict in Anambra State local Government Service Commission.

3. Inability of Management to carry the workers along in decision making has occasioned labour conflict in Anambra State Local Government Service Commission.

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2. Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Framework

Concept of Conflict

Conflict is a disagreement or clash between individuals, groups, or entities that arises from differences in opinions, values, beliefs, or interests. It can manifest in various forms, including interpersonal disputes, organizational tensions, and societal unrest. Conflict is a behavior intended to obstruct the achievement of some other person's goals. Conflict is defined as the presence of disharmony or disagreement that occurs when goals, interests or values of different individuals or groups are incompatible and frustrate each other in order to achieve common objectives in an organization (Kazimoto, 2013 in Adilo, 2019). Unresolved conflict in an organization creates many thoughtful consequences involving high financial and human costs (Adilo, 2019).

Fatile and Adejuwon in Zayum (2022) viewed the conflict as what occurs when people have incompatible ideals over the sharing of scarce resources to meet teeming demands. Mullins and Christy (2013) maintain that conflict is a behavior projected to obstruct the achievement of some other person's plans. It is an inevitable part of living because it is related to situations of scarce resources, division of functions, power relations, and role-differentiation (Bercovitch in Zayum, 2022). It also refers to any situation in which there are incompatible goals, cognitions,

or emotions within or between individuals or groups that lead to opposition or antagonistic interaction. The definition recognizes three basic types of conflict: Goal conflict is a situation in which desired end states or preferred outcomes appear to be incompatible while cognitive conflict is a situation in which ideas or thoughts are inconsistent. Whereas, affective conflict is a situation in which feelings or emotions are incompatible; that is, people become angry with one another. Conflict arises from differences, both large and small. As such, it occurs whenever people disagree over their values, motivations, perceptions, ideas, or desire goals (Segal & Smith in Zayum, 2022). Conflict refers to some form of friction, disagreement, or discord arising within a group when the beliefs or actions of one or more members of the group are either resisted by or unacceptable to one or more members of another group (Digvijaysinh, 2013).

Awan and Anjum (2015) say that properly managed conflict promotes open communication, collaborative decision making, regular feedback, and timely resolution of conflict. Open communication and collaboration enhance the flow of new ideas and strengthen work relationships, which can have a positive effect on employee morale. Regular feedback and timely resolution of conflict has the potential of improving employee satisfaction and job performance (Awan & Saeed, 2015). Conflict has both positive and negative impacts on the performance of any organization, but for any

organization to develop, it must be able to manage and resolve any conflict that occurs within and outside the organization without much delay (Oladimeji, Adeoti & Babatunde, 2020). Conflict situations or problems denoted incompatibility of goals and opposing behaviors within an organization.

Conflicts are of various types, below are types of conflicts as stated in Osabiya (2015):

i. **Hierarchical Conflict:** There may be conflict between the various levels of the organization. The board of director may be in conflict with top management, middle management may be in conflict with supervisory personnel, or there may be general conflict between management and workers.

ii. **Functional Conflict:** There may be conflict between the various functional department of the organization conflict between the production and marketing department in an industrial organization is a classic example.

iii. **Line- Staff Conflict:** There may be conflict between line and staff. It often results from situations in which staff personnel do not formerly possess authority over line personnel.

iv. **Formal- Informal Conflict:** There may be conflict between the formal and informal organizations for example the informal organizations norms for performance may be incompatible with the formal organizations norms for performance. Conflict can be viewed into fire sequential stages which are; latent,

perceived, felt, and manifest and conflict resolution stages.

v. **Latent:** In this stage the basic conditions for potential conflict are resources, role conflict, drivers for autonomy, divergence of individual goal etc these conditions are lower suppressed for reasons not quite known to members or belong to the opposition on every issue.

vi. **Perceived:** At this stage focused anxieties are created between the anxiety and tension. Each party begins to develop negative feelings towards each other. As the parties in conflict argues and battle for their points of view the significance of the disputed issue is likely to be blown out of proportion. vii. **Manifest:** This is the stage of open conflict, a stage when conflict behaviour is exhibited such overt behaviour includes sabotage.

viii. **Resolution and Aftermath:** This stage represent the condition that exists after the resolution or suppression of the conflict if the conflicts have been genuinely resolved, if can lead to an improved relationship and effective cooperation between organizational members. But if not resolved adequately, it may lead to a new and more severe conflict than the first.

In a similar vein conflict could be intrapersonal or interpersonal, inter-group or inter organizational.

Intrapersonal are conflict that are internal to individual i.e. mutually exclusive positive goal conflict, positive negative goal conflict and negative- conflict.

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Interpersonal are conflict between two or more people in the organization. Intergroup are conflict between groups in the same organization. Inter-organizational conflicts are conflict between organizations.

1.1.2 Conflict Management

Conflict management is viewed as a broad concept encompassing conflict resolution and the transformation of conflict into a positive and beneficial force, it entails proactive measures taken to prevent conflicts at the right moment and facilitating their efficient and amicable resolution (Ahot & Kithinji, 2021). Chaudhary and Arora (2023) stated that conflict management is the ability of an organization to identify the sources of conflict and put strategic measures in place to minimize or control conflict. To Alper and Law as cited in Kalu and Queen (2024), conflict management involves acquiring skills related to conflict resolution, establishing structures of conflict models, and putting strategic measures as well as approaches in place. Conflict management focuses on the principle that conflicts cannot necessarily be resolved entirely but can be managed using appropriate actions such as accommodating, avoiding, collaborating, compromise and confrontation (Igbinoba, 2023). It is also concerned with the implementation of certain strategies to reduce the bad side of the conflict and increase its positive aspect in other to increase staff performance and effectiveness in the organization.

Chukwuemeka and Aniche (2016) define conflict management as the interventions designed to reduce conflict, or in some instances, to increase insufficient conflict. It is a process whereby managers design plans and implement policies and procedures to ensure that conflict situations are resolved effectively. Effective management of conflict can bring about positive results like promotion of open communication, collaborative decision making, regular feedback, and timely settlement of the conflict. While unmanaged conflict can promote dysfunctional communication and poor behavior among employees which can have an effect on overall employee morale thereby resulting in lower productivity.

Mills and Mene (2020) views conflict management as techniques to resolve conflicts in the organization to facilitate organisational goals and objectives. Similarly, Gary (2021) assert that interventions aimed at reducing conflict or, in some cases, increasing insufficient conflict are referred to as conflict management. It is a process where managers create strategies and put them into action to make sure that disputes are settled successfully. Furthermore, Awalluddin and Maznorbalia (2023) asserts that in order to optimize learning and organizational success, conflict management requires the cultivation of effective strategies to reduce the dysfunctions of conflict and amplify its constructive functions. This implies that conflict management entails reducing the chances of

counterproductive escalation, as opposed to strictly avoiding or terminating it (Gary 2021). Therefore, conflict management encompasses the procedures employed by groups and individuals to address complaints or disagreements, with the goal of reaching a compromise that not only facilitates resolution but also cultivates consensus and underscores a genuine dedication to decision-making. Other sources of conflict in the local government include:

Sources of Conflict in the Local Government Service Commission

Poor Financial Base/Local Government financial Autonomy

This is another source of conflicts in the local government. This is true and imperative, because it is inevitable to have and experience discrepancy between the wishes and fulfillment of workers in an environment of scarcity, which implies that the desires of the parties (workers and management) are more or less unlimited, while the means of satisfaction are limited. Today the regular story is “zero” allocation which in no small measure has impaired payment of workers’ salaries, fringe benefits and provision of social services by the local government.

Lack of Communication

Chukwu (2001) contends that lack of communication over issues and absence of effective organizational frameworks to handle grievance make workers feel despondent and

aggrieved. This can bring about mistrust, misinformation and crisis.

Payment of salary and other Workers’ Benefits

There is no gainsaying that in many local governments across the country today are owing their workers salary areas ranging from six to twenty-five months. Ezeja (2002) contends that local government workers in Enugu State are being owed areas of salaries between seven to twenty five months.

Chukwuemeka and Aniche (2016) postulates that the most fundamental reason why conflicts arise in employment situation is that the employers are ‘using’ employees for various purposes of their own whilst the employees in turn though from a weaker point or position are ‘using’ their employment for their own various purposes.

In most countries the right to work is seen as freedom for individuals to earn a living by work freely entered into. Wetlaufer (2001) and Johnson (1993), argue that the state’s contribution should be to create a climate under which individuals are able to exercise such a freedom. The work environment should not be a battle ground where the employee and employer should see each other as enemies. The two should rather see themselves as partners in progress and thus management have to ensure that use of participatory approach to decision making reigns supreme. Supporting this view Chukwuemeka, Anazodo and Nzewi (2011)

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identified three major organizational leadership styles, namely autocratic, Laissez – faire, and democratic. He favours the democratic leader. The leader gets members involved in decision making. While the autocratic leadership is synonymous to conflict.

External sources of labour conflicts in work places include government industrial economy legislation, their ambiguous element which result in widespread inter/intra disputes, other issues are the National economic mismanagement, general pattern of distribution of wealth and power in the society (Chukwuemeka and Aniche, 2016) He further states that some of these external factors/sources of conflict are not supposed to directly instigate labour conflict, but they may influence actual expectation substantially determined by the nature of work as demands and having an influence on the intensity of conflicts and the whole process of the conflict of industrial relations.

However, events in the middle and late 1980s in Nigeria showed that amidst the serious consequences of state economic Structural Adjustment Programme and the annulment of the June 12th 1993 presidential election, veteran industrial unions such as National Union of Petroleum Energy and Natural Gas (NUPENG), Nigerian Union of Local Government Employees (NULGE) and the Nigerian Labour Congress (NLC) attempted to crumble the social and economic activities of the country.

Chukwuemeka and Aniche (2016) identifies some of the factors that could lead to labour conflict in the public sector and industries. These are itemized under two broad headings – internal and external causes. The internal causes include, style of management, that is to say uncompromising, autocratic, non-participatory employer. These heighten labour conflicts. The social consciousness of the workers is yet another factor.

Otobo (21988) supports this opinion. He adds that when the management is provided with all the necessary welfare amenities, while the lower ranking workers are not considered for even the barest facilities that conflict could readily ensue.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design

The design for this work is based on survey research design. Descriptive survey enables the researchers to collect data from a reasonable number of respondents within the targeted population, in such a way that the result of the data collected could be generalized to the entire

3.2 Population of the Study

The population of this study constituted the civil servants in the Local Government Service Commission, Awka Anambra State. According to Personnel unit of Anambra state Local Government Service Commission (ASLGSC) 2024, the total population of staff in the commission was 126. The 126 staff of the Local Government Service Commission formed the population of this study.

3.3 Sample Size

The study population of 126 is manageable and therefore we adopted census study.

3.4 Method of Data Collection

The researcher employed direct questionnaire distribution method in collecting data. This approach affords the researcher the opportunity of making some clarifications or explanations where necessary. The instrument of data collection was administered by the researcher. The questionnaire was structured on five point–Likert scale with weights assigned to; strongly Agree (SA) = 5points, Agree (A) = 4points, Disagree (D) = 3points, Strongly Disagree (SD) = 2points and Undecided (U) 1 Point.

3.5 Method of Data Analysis

After data were collected from the field, they were presented using descriptive statistics such

4. Data Analysis

4.1 Data Presentation

4.1.1 Descriptive Analysis of Data on Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Table 4.1: Gender Distribution of the Respondents

Sex	Frequency	Percentage (%)
MALE	56	46.7
FEMALE	64	53.3
TOTAL	120	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.1 shows the percentage of respondent based on gender. Male respondent for this study was 46.7% meanwhile female respondent

as tables, means, frequencies and simple percentage.

A mean score of 2.5 bench mark was used to determine the agreement level of the respondents.

The mean was calculated as:

$$\frac{5+4+3+2+1}{5} = \frac{15}{5} = 3$$

Decision Rule:

Based on the mean score 3.0, the decision was that any item with a mean score below 3.0 was regarded as disagreement while 3.0 and above was regarded as agreement. The hypotheses were tested using inferential statistics of Pearson product moment correlation (PPMC) with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20, at 0.5 level of significance.

represents 53.3%. This study shows that female respondents were the highest respondents involved.

Table 4.2: Age Distribution of the Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
20 – 30yrs	20	16.7
31 – 40yrs	42	35
41 – 50yrs	30	25
51 and above	28	23.3
TOTAL	120	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The 31-40 year group constituted 35% of respondents and was highest number of respondents followed by 41-50 with 30% and then the 50 and above which made up 25% of the

respondents. The lowest number of respondents was between 20 and 30 years which made 16.7% of employees.

Table 4.3: Educational Qualification Distribution of the Respondents

Education Level	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Secondary School Certificate	0	0
OND/NCE	25	20.8
HND/B.Sc	62	51.7
Postgraduate Education	33	27.5
TOTAL	120	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

According to table 4.3, 20.8% of the respondents had Ordinary National Diploma and National Certificate Education, 51.7% of the respondents had First degree and Higher National Diploma, while 27% of them had attained the level of postgraduate education, none had secondary

school certificate as the highest educational qualification. The higher percentage of first degree holders and its equivalent is an indicator that the respondents were qualified and well educated and therefore understood the question items well.

Table 4.4: Working Experience

Length of service	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1 – 5years	20	16.7
6 – 10years	26	21.6
11 – 15years	34	28.3
16 – 20years	30	25
21years and above	10	8.4
TOTAL	120	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Based on Table 4.4, the highest percentage of working experience for respondents was 11 – 15 years which is 28.3%. It shows that majority of respondents were experienced employees. Then it was followed by employees that had working experience for 16 – 20 years which contribute 25%. Other respondents that had worked for 6 – 10 years constituted 21.6% and the least was

employees with above 21 year experience which is 8.4%.

4.1.2 Descriptive Analysis of the Research Variables - Collaboration conflict management strategy, accommodating conflict management strategy, avoidance conflict management strategy and Organizational Performance

4.1.2.1 Descriptive Analysis on Collaboration Conflict Management Strategy

Table 4.5: Descriptive Analysis on Collaboration Conflict Management Strategy

S/N	Statement	Scale					Mean		Decision
		SA 5	A 4	D 3	SD 2	U 1	$\sum Fx$	X	
1	The LG Service Commission encourages the use of collaborative approaches to conflict resolution.	58 48.3%	40 33.3%	10 8.3%	5 4.2%	7 5.8%	497	4.14	Agreed
2	The Commission joins ideas of conflicting parties in order to achieve the best solution in resolving conflict	52 43.3%	45 37.5%	5 4.2%	8 6.7%	10 8.3%	481	4	Agreed
3	Collaboration helps in achievement of mutual outcomes in conflict given its focus on building relations and integrating solutions	50 41.7%	50 41.7%	5 4.2%	10 8.3%	5 4.2%	490	4.08	Agreed
4	Embracing dialogue in managing conflict results into positive conflict outcomes	54 45%	46 38.3%	10 8.3%	0	10 8.3%	494	4.11	Agreed
5	The Commission collaborates others' viewpoints in resolving conflict.	48 40%	48 40%	12 10%	5 4.2%	7 5.8%	485	4.04	Agreed
Grand Mean							4.074		Agreed

Source: Field Survey, 2025

To analyze the findings, participants who strongly agreed and those who agreed were combined into one category of those who concurred with the items. In addition, employees who disagreed and those who strongly disagreed were combined into another category of those who opposed the items. The study findings in Table 4.5 on Collaboration Conflict Management Strategy showed that majority 98 (81.6%) of the respondents agreed that LG Service Commission

encourages the use of collaborative approaches to conflict resolution, 15 (12.5%) of them disagreed while 7 (5.8%) of the respondents were undecided. 97(80.8%) respondents agreed that the Commission joins ideas of conflicting parties in order to achieve the best solution in resolving conflict, while 13 (10.9%) disagreed with the statement., 10 (8.3%) were undecided. Majority 100 (83.3%) of respondents also agreed that Collaboration helps in achievement of

mutual outcomes in conflict given its focus on building relations and integrating solutions while 15 (12.5%) disagreed, 5 (4.2%) of the respondents were undecided. 100 respondents representing 83.3% agreed that embracing dialogue in managing conflict results into positive conflict outcomes, 10 of the respondents representing 8.3% were not in agreement with the statement, 8.3% of the respondents neither agreed nor disagreed. The analysis also revealed that 90 respondents representing 80% agreed

that the Commission collaborates others' viewpoints in resolving conflict, while 17 respondents representing 14.2% disagreed with the statement, while 5.8% of them were undecided. In addition, Table 4.5 showed that all the 5 items had their means ranged from 4.0–4.14 and grand mean of 3.074 were all above the benchmark point of 3.0 on a 5-point rating scale. This indicates respondents' agreement with the items on collaboration conflict management strategy.

4.1.2.2 Descriptive Analysis on Accommodating Conflict Management Strategy

Table 4.6: Descriptive Analysis on Leadership/management style

S/N	Statement	Scale					Mean		Decision
		SA 5	A 4	D 3	SD 2	U 1	$\sum Fx$	X	
6	Autocratic management style is used	40 33.3%	48 40%	10 8.3%	8 6.7%	14 11.7%	452	3.76	Agreed
7	Dictatorial management style	50 41.7%	40 33.3%	10 8.3%	10 8.3%	10 8.3%	470	3.92	Agreed
8	Democratic management style	40 33.3%	46 38.7%	8 6.7%	12 10%	14 11.7%	446	3.71	Agreed
9	Laises faire management style	55 45.8%	40 33.3%	5 4.2%	5 4.2%	15 12.5%	475	3.95	Agreed
10	Mixed method of management style	20 16.7%	12 10%	30 25%	30 25%	28 23.3%	326	2.71	Disagreed
Grand Mean							3.61		Agreed

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.6 focused autocratic leadership style in Local Government Service Commission Awka. The table showed that majority 88 (73.3%) of the respondents agreed that autocratic leadership style is frequently used in my organization to

resolve disputes 18 (15 %) of them disagreed, while 14 (11.7%) were undecided. 90 representing 75% of the respondents agreed that the Commission accommodates employees view point in resolving conflict amicable, 20

representing 16.7% of them disagreed, while 10 representing 8.3% of them were undecided. Majority 86 (72%) of the respondents agreed that the dictatorial management style is employees in solving conflict, while 20 (16.7%) respondents disagreed, 11 (11.7%) of them were undecided. The analysis also revealed that 95 respondents representing 79.1% agreed that management use democratic style where the management seek consent and approval, and are eager to help and support in resolving conflict, while 8.4% of them disagreed, 12.5% of them

were undecided. Majority 60 respondents representing 50% disagreed that the laisses faire leadership method is used in the organization while 32 respondents representing 26.7% were in agreement with the statement, 28 representing 23.3% of the participants were undecided. Table 4.6 showed that 4 items had their means ranged from 3.71 and above, while 1 item had 2.71 with grand mean of 3.61. This indicates that the respondents were in agreement with the items on accommodating conflict management strategy.

4.1.2.3 Descriptive Analysis on Avoidance Conflict Management Strategy

Table 4.7: Descriptive Analysis on Avoidance Conflict Management Strategy

S/N	Statement	Scale					Mean		Decision
		SA 5	A 4	D 3	SD 2	U 1	$\sum Fx$	X	
11	The Commission usually ignore conflict instead of solving it	0	5 4.2%	25 20.8%	70 59.3%	20 16.7%	270	2.25	Disagreed
12	Management of the Commission always withdraw in conflict in order to avoid further engagement in an inappropriate interaction	0	0	40 33.3%	50 41.7%	30 25%	250	2.08	Disagreed
13	The Commission always avoid confrontation in conflict	10 8.3%	20 16.7%	40 33.3%	40 33.3%	10 8.3%	340	2.83	Disagreed
14	It always delay in handling complaint which lead to conflict	15 12.5%	10 8.3%	45 37.5%	40 33.3%	10 8.3%	340	2.83	Disagreed
15	The Commission usually sidestepping on issues related to conflict	10 8.3%	10 8.3%	42 35%	46 38.3%	12 10%	320	2.66	Disagreed
	Grand Mean							2.53	Disagreed

Source: Field Survey, 2025

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Table 4.7 presented the results of avoidance conflict management strategy in LG Service Commission Awka. The table showed that majority 96 (80.1%) of the respondents disagreed that the Commission usually ignore conflict instead of solving it, 5 (4.2%) of them agreed with the statement, while 20 (16.7%) of the respondents were undecided. 90 representing 75% of the respondents disagreed that management of the Commission always withdraw in conflict in order to avoid further engagement in an inappropriate interaction, none of the respondents agreed with the statement, while 30 representing 25% of them were undecided. Majority 80 (66.6%) of the respondents disagreed that the Commission always avoid confrontation in conflict while 30 (25%) respondents agreed, 10 of them representing 8.3% neither agreed nor disagreed

with the statement. 25 respondents representing 20.8% were of the opinion that LG Service Commission always delay in handling complaint which leads to conflict, while the majority 85 (70.8%) of the respondents disagreed with the statement, 10 (8.3%) of them were undecided. Again majority 88 respondents representing 73.3% disagreed that the Commission usually sidestepping on issues related to conflict, while 20 representing 16.6% of respondents were in agreement with the statement, 12 (10%) of them were undecided. Table 4.7 also showed that all the items had their means ranged from 2.0 – 2.83 with grand mean of 2.53 were all below the benchmark point of 3.0 on a 5-point rating scale. This indicates the respondents' disagreement with the items on avoidance conflict management strategy displayed in the above Table.

4.1.2.4 Descriptive Analysis on Organizational Performance

Table 4.8: Descriptive Analysis on Organizational Performance

S/N	Statement	Scale					Mean		Decision
		SA 5	A 4	D 3	SD 2	U 1	$\sum Fx$	X	
16	Effective conflict management techniques have a positive impact on our organization's performance.	53 44.2%	40 33.3%	0	11 9.2%	16 13.3%	463	3.86	Agreed
17	Achieving our organization's objectives requires effective conflict management.	40 33.3%	45 37.5%	5 4.2%	10 8.3%	20 16.7%	435	3.63	Agreed
18	The methods employed to address employees' issues influence their effectiveness within the Service Commission.	42 35%	43 35.8%		15 12.5%	20 16.7%	432	3.6	Agreed
19	Organizational performance is unrelated to the organization's capacity for dispute resolution.	10 8.3%	15 12.5%	50 41.7%	40 33.3%	5 4.2%	345	2.88	Disagreed
20	When handled effectively, conflicts can result in better organizational outcomes.	40 33.3%	40 33.3%		10 8.3%	30 25%	410	3.42	Agreed
Grand Mean							3.478		Agreed

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.8 focused on the analysis of organizational performance in LG Service Commission, Awka. The table displayed that majority 93 (77.5%) of the respondents agreed that effective conflict management techniques have a positive impact on our organization's performance, while 11 (9.2%) of them disagreed with the statement, 16 (13.3%) of them were

undecided. 85 representing 70.8% respondents agreed that achieving the organization's objectives requires effective conflict management, 20 (16.7%) of them were undecided while 15 representing 12.5% of them disagreed with the statement. The majority 85 (70.8%) of the respondents agreed that the methods employed to address

employees’ issues influence their effectiveness within the Service Commission, while 20 (16.7%) of them were undecided, 15 (12.5%) respondents disagreed. The analysis also revealed that majority 90 (75%) of respondents disagreed that organizational performance is unrelated to the organization's capacity for dispute resolution, 25 (20.8%) of the respondents agreed, while the remaining 5(4.2%) of the respondents were undecided. The majority 88 respondents representing 66.6% also agreed that when handled effectively, conflicts can result in better organizational outcomes, 10 (8.3%) and 30 (25%) of the respondents disagreed with the statement and undecided respectively. Table 4.7

Table 4.9: Test of Hypothesis One Correlations

	Collaboration management strategy	conflict	Organizational Performance
Lack of local government financial autonomy	Pearson Correlation	1	
Conflict	Sig. (2-tailed)	.512	.512
	N	120	120
	Pearson Correlation	.026	.026
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.026	1
	N	120	120

*.Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). a. Listwise N=120

The result of the correlation coefficient for hypothesis one indicates that the Pearson Product

also displayed the mean scores of the five items ranged from 2.88– 3.86 with grand mean of 3.478, indicating the respondents’ agreement with the items on organizational performance as displayed in the table.

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

The hypotheses in this study were tested and analyzed using Pearson Correlation with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

4.2.1 Hypothesis One

Labour conflict in Anambra State Local Government Service Commission is a result of financial autonomy

Moment Correlation Coefficient is 0.512 showing that there is a positive relationship between absence of financial autonomy and conflict in

Anambra State local Government Service Commission.

Decision Rule: From the computation above, the probability value at 0.026 is less than 0.05 significant level. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis, and conclude that lack of financial autonomy is responsible for frequent labour

Table 4.10: Test of Hypothesis Two Correlations

	Accommodating management strategy	conflict	Organizational Performance
Management style	1		.721
and Pearson Correlation			.011
Sig. (2-tailed)			
N	120		120
Conflict	.721	1	
Pearson Correlation			
Sig. (2-tailed)	.011		
N	120		120

*.Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). a. Listwise N=120

The result of the correlation coefficient for hypothesis two indicates that the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient is 0.721 showing that there is a positive relationship between leadership/management styles in Anambra State Local Government Service Commission.

Decision Rule: From the computation above, the probability value at 0.011 is less than 0.05

conflict in Anambra State Local Government Service Commission.

4.2.2 Hypothesis Two

Leadership/management style is raison d’et re for labour conflict in Anambra State Local Government Service Commission.

significant level. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the research hypothesis.

4.2.3 Hypothesis Three

Inability of Anambra State Local Government Service Commission to carry the workers along in decision making has occasioned labour conflict.

Table 4.11: Test of Hypothesis Three Correlations

	Excluding workers in decision making	Organizational Performance
Conflict	Pearson Correlation	-0.675
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.210
	N	120
	Pearson Correlation	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	
	N	120

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). a. Listwise N=120

The result of the correlation coefficient for hypothesis three indicates that the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient is - 0.675 showing strong negative relationship between leadership/management’s inability to carry the workers along in decision making.

Decision Rule: From the computation above, the probability value at 0.210 is greater than 0.05 significant level. Therefore, we reject the alternative hypothesis and accept the null hypothesis.

5. Findings, Conclusion and Recommendations.

5.1 Summary of Findings

Based on the statistical analysis of the research variables and the testing of hypotheses using descriptive statistics (mean ratings) and inferential statistics (Pearson product moment correlation), the following findings were made.

1. Labour conflict in Anambra State Local Government Service Commission is as a result of lack of financial autonomy.

2. Leadership/management style is raison d’et re for labour conflict in Anambra State Local Government Service Commission.

3. Inability of the management of Anambra State Local Government Service Commission Awka to carry the workers along in decision making has little or no effect on frequent labour conflict.

5.2 Conclusion

The findings of this study highlight the critical role of conflict management strategies in influencing organizational performance within the Anambra State Local Government Service Commission, Awka, workplace. It is therefore pertinent to remark that the factors interrogated as causes of labour conflict should be addressed.

5.3 Recommendations

1. Management of Anambra State Local Government Service Commission Awka should put up position papers and push for the actualization of local government financial autonomy.

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2. The management should be mindful of the type of leadership style adopted, especially the style that is not workers friendly. Therefore, workers-friendly leadership/management style should be adopted.

3. Though the hypothesis on carrying the workers along in decision making was not a

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major factor in labour conflict in Anambra State Local Government Service Commission Awka, however, it is necessary for management to adopt participatory or democratic approach in decision making.

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